

A STUDY OF BIOFILM FORMATION IN CSOM PATIENTS

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Dissertation submitted to the
B.L.D.E (Deemed to be University),
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In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of

MASTER OF SURGERY

IN

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

It is with glorious veneration and intense gratitude, I would like to thank my esteemed teacher and guide **Dr.H T LATHADEVI**, Professor, Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU)'s Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura: who was ever encouraging in his approach while helping me through my postgraduate course. She was always supportive and allowed me to work and develop at my own pace, guiding wherever necessary. Without her guidance and support, it would have been impossible to complete this dissertation. I express my sincere gratitude to **Dr. R N KARADI** Professor and Head of Department, Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, for his support and encouragement throughout the preparation of the work.

I am immensely thankful to **Dr. Aravind Patil**, Principal, BLDE (DU) Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, for allowing me do this work, to use facilities in this institution and for his encouragement and support throughout my postgraduate course.

I am highly indebted to **Dr. S.P. Guggarigoudar** , Retired Principal and Head of Department, Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura for his valuable guidance and support throughout my postgraduate course in acquiring clinical knowledge.

.I express my sincere gratitude to Assitant professors , **Dr. Shashi Kumar and Dr.Shivashankar, Dr.Manali Bhat and senior residents Dr. Sunitha Dr.Sharanbassu**Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery, BLDE(DU) Shri B. M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura,

for their concern, suggestions and constructive encouragement.

I am immensely thankful to my Postgraduate colleagues and friends, **Dr. Mohan Raaj , Dr. Justin , Dr. Surekha , Dr.Radhikakrishnan, Dr.Sushma , Dr.Sagarika , Dr. Reshma , Dr. Adishree , Dr.Nivedha Dr meghana , Dr amit, Dr tomin, Dr manisha Dr neelima**for their immense help and support during my postgraduate course. I thank them from my heart.

I am eternally grateful to my beloved family; my parents **Mr. dr Ramesh patil**and **Mrs Indumati patil** who have nurtured me and supported me in all my endeavours, without their love and innumerable sacrifices, I would not be the person I am today.

I would like to thank, Audiologists **rakshitha** Statistician **Mrs. Vijaya Sorganvi**, Asst. Librarian for their support during my post graduate course. I am filled with gratitude to all my study subjects whose co-operation has contributed to this study.

Finally, I bow my head in a silent acknowledgement of all that **The Lord Almighty** has blessed me with.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CSOM	Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media
TM	Tympanic Membrane
ASOM	Acute Suppurative Otitis Media
COM	Chronic Otitis Media
CNS	Central Nervous System
WHO	World Health Organisation
AOM	Acute Otitis Media
TM	Tube Method
CRA	Congo red agar
MtP	Microtitre Plate
EAC	External Auditory Canal
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
HRCT	High Resolution Computed Tomography
PTA	Pure Tone Audiometry

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is characterized by prolonged inflammation of middle ear mucosa and mastoid leading to TM perforation and ear discharge.¹⁻³ CSOM is now supposed to be biofilm-related.

In biofilms, bacteria are embedded in a slim-like extracellular matrix composed of proteins, polysaccharides and nucleic acids called extracellular polymeric substances.¹¹

In this community, bacteria do not randomly make groups but organize into complex three-dimensional structures.¹¹

The most common microorganisms found in isolates from ear discharge in CSOM are *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Aspergillus spp.*, *Candida spp.* and these vary in different geographical distributions¹¹

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

1. To study the incidence of biofilms in bacterial isolates of CSOM cases
2. To study bacteriological pattern and their antibiotic susceptibility in biofilm-producing organisms in CSOM
3. To study Resistant pattern to antimicrobials among biofilm-producing strains leading to treatment failure
4. To study the outcome of early surgical intervention in such patients.

METHODOLOGY:

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

This prospective study was conducted in the Department of Otorhinolaryngology in association with the Department of Microbiology in a tertiary care, Shri B M Patil medical college and research centre and Hospital [Bldc (DU) university] in Vijayapura from september 2022 to march 2024

1. The data will be collected in the form of questionnaire in terms of complete clinical history, clinical examination and necessary investigations of the patient.
2. Detailed examination of the patients with an emphasis on ear findings will be done with the help of otoscopy to see the tympanic membrane status
3. Ear discharge sample is collected using aseptic precautions and culture sensitivity and tests to check for presence of biofilm is done
4. A preoperative pure tone audiometry and HRCT temporal bone (coronal) and (axial) view has been done in required cases.
5. Early intervention of the patients with biofilms by tympanoplasty, cortical mastoidectomy, Modified radical mastoidectomy will be performed.
6. Post operatively these patients will be followed up at one week, 15 days, one month, three months. They will be evaluated for the discharge-free period, pain-free period, graft uptake and infection-free period during follow-up.

RESULT

Out of 170 patients, 155 patients were biofilm positive, the most common organism isolated being Methicillin resistant staphylococcus aureus and least common being Coagulase negative staphylococcus aureus and preoperatively 99 patients had pain (excluding biofilm negative patients) early surgical intervention was performed who were followed up at 1 week, 15 days, 1 month and 3 months for postoperative pain and it is found that at 1 week 47 patients, at 15 days 30 patients, at 1 month 9 patients

and at 3 months 8 patients have pain ,there is reduction in postoperative pain which is statistically significant. Postoperative graft uptake is seen in 142(83.5%) patients

CONCLUSION

Early surgical intervention in biofilm positive csom patients would be helpful in reducing pain due to infection , and regain infection free ear

INTRODUCTION

In otolaryngology, chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is one of the most common diseases and affects the population worldwide. The CSOM incidence is found to be affecting approximately 20 million people globally ¹⁻³

CSOM is defined as mucosal inflammation in the middle ear and mastoid and persists for more than 2-3 months, leading to tympanic membrane perforation and ear discharge. This leads to profound health implications and complications intracranially or extracranially, in turn causing morbidity among the affected population. Thus, immediate attention is required to control the disease prevalence worldwide, and such outcomes make it a significant public health issue ⁽⁴⁻⁷⁾.

The occurrence of CSOM varies across different nations, but countries with low- and middle-income levels have more disease prevalence. ⁽⁸⁻⁹⁾

CSOM can develop as a complication of inadequately treated Acute Suppurative Otitis Media (ASOM) or de novo chronic in onset. CSOM is now supposed to be biofilm-related. ⁽¹⁰⁾

Biofilm is a slime-like extracellular matrix made of proteins, polysaccharides, and nucleic acids, which form an extracellular polymeric substance where bacteria form aggregates and are organized into complex three-dimensional structures. ⁽¹¹⁾

Pseudomonas aeruginosa, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Aspergillus spp.*, *Candida spp.* are the most common microorganisms found in CSOM patients with ear discharge, and they vary in different geographical conditions⁽¹¹⁾

Certain evidence supports the theory that Chronic otitis media with effusion, cholesteatoma, chronic suppurative otitis media and otitis media with effusion and other chronic ear diseases are biofilm related ¹²

Recently bacterial biofilms have been proven to be important in infectious diseases in the ear¹³ . Bacterial resistance is emerging and posing problems in controlling the intractable infections. Most of the times culture based antibiotics may not be helpful. Hence getting rid of biofilm from the infection site would be better option in such cases.

The study outcomes of early intervention in biofilm positive CSOM patients is sparse in literature, hence the study.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

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REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HISTORY

Anthony van Leeuwenhoek (1632–1723) from Delft, The Netherlands was the one to observe and describe biofilms with the help of primitive microscope from his own mouth sample 1683–1708 there he found microbial aggregates over the “scurf of the teeth” and also from “particles scraped off his tongue”¹⁴

Henrici with the help of ‘direct microscopy’ studied fresh water biofouling and observed “it is quite evident that for the most part water bacteria are not free floating organisms, but grow attached upon submerged surfaces”.¹⁶

ZoBell & Allen observed ‘adherence and growth of bacteria on submerged glass slides in seawater’¹⁷. The study purpose was to observe the development of fouling in early stage and initiation was “by biofilm growing bacteria and to a lesser extent, other microorganisms and that such films favor the subsequent attachment of the larger and more inimical fouling organisms. The film of bacteria may promote the attachment of macroscopic organisms in different ways...”¹⁷

In 1977¹⁸ the image of biofilm was introduced for the first time and observed that ‘aggregated bacteria (heaps) surrounded by abundance of slime could be observed in sputum of Cystic Fibrosis patients chronically infected with mucoid phenotypes of *P. aeruginosa*’¹⁸

In 1980 Costerton’s group using electron microscopy published observations of a postmortem Cystic Fibrosis lung affected by *P. aeruginosa* colonies¹⁹ and “surveys on the bacterial glycocalyx in nature and disease”²⁰ and then he changed ‘glycocalyx’ to ‘biofilms’ in subsequent survey²¹

In 1981 “The first two medical reports using the word biofilm were published by dentists from the University of Lund, Sweden^{22,23} in the same year when Costerton first used the term ‘biofilm’ in a technical microbiology report”²⁴

In 1985 “Costerton introduced ‘biofilm’ growth in medical microbiology in²⁵, demonstrated the increased antimicrobial resistance of biofilm growing compared to planktonically growing bacteria, and subsequently pioneered the work on physiology, biochemistry etc. of biofilm-growing bacteria”²⁵. “Thereafter ‘biofilm’ gradually became accepted as the most adequate word for the description of sessile growth in vivo”²⁶

In 1996 “Costerton organized the first ASM biofilm conference in Snowbird, Utah, USA. At that time he was giving lectures all over the world about biofilm and biofilm infections and had initiated collaborations with scientists and physicians from many different medical specialties and also with industry”¹⁵

Rayner et al documented the role played by biofilms for the first time in chronic otitis media in mucosal otolaryngological infections was the first to demonstrate association of biofilm with otitis media²⁷

Dohar et al used nonhuman primate model to study perforated tympanic membrane in COM. ‘Cynomolgus monkeys underwent perforation of the tympanic membrane and inoculation of the middle ear with a biofilm-forming strain of *P. aeruginosa*, and biofilm formation was successfully demonstrated in this animal model’.²⁸

Chole²⁹ and Faddis²⁹ observed ‘biofilm formation frequency in human cholesteatoma specimens and in gerbil experimental cholesteatoma specimens as 67 % and 95% respectively’.

In 2009, Homøe et al³⁰ observed “ biofilm formation in five of the six pediatric COM cases and in nine of the ten adult COM cases”.

Lee et al³¹ in a study ‘observed 10 COM patients and ten controls for biofilm formation and found that biofilms were present in 60% of the study group and in 10% of the control group members’

Anatomy of ear

External ear

The auricle and external acoustic meatus form the external ear, sound is collected and amplified and is then reaches the middle ear.(fig.1)

Fig.1 External ear (source Medscape)

Middle ear

The middle ear plays role in sound conduction to the fluid of the inner ear from external ear. It inhabits the petrous part of temporal bone and is air filled cavity as it communicates with nasopharynx through Eustachian tube³²(fig.2)

Fig.2 middle ear (Source : Medscape)

The walls of the tympanic cavity are:

- Tympanic membrane forms the lateral wall
- Posteriorly it is connected with mastoid antrum via aditus
- The medial wall/labyrinthine wall has the oval window which is covered with stapes footplate; posterior to and separated by the promontory is the round window covered by secondary tympanic membrane
- The Carotid wall or anterior wall, here the carotid canal is separated from tympanic cavity by a thin bony plate
- The roof of the tympanic cavity is tegmen; it separates middle cranial fossa from the epitympanic recess
- The floor is formed by the thin bony plate that separates internal jugular vein and the middle ear

Tympanic membrane

The external ear is separated from middle ear by an semi-transparent, oval tympanic membrane. It has 2 parts pars tensa where malleus handle is firmly attached to the membrane; where it forms concavity the umbo. Pars flaccida is part of the membrane which lies above lateral process of malleus (fig.3)

Fig.3 tympanic membrane (Source: Medscape)

Sound waves collected by the pinna are transferred to the mobile tympanic membrane, which then transmitted to the ear ossicles.

The tympanic membrane has following sensory supply

- Auriculotemporal nerve (mandibular branch of trigeminal nerve)
- Auricular branch of vagus nerve (Arnold nerve)
- Tympanic branch of glossopharyngeal nerve (Jacobson nerve)

The blood supply is from the stylomastoid branch of the posterior auricular, anterior tympanic and deep auricular branches from the maxillary artery. Venous drainage is derived from external jugular vein, the dural veins and the transverse sinus.

Middle ear

Muscles, nerves, and the auditory tube occupy space within the middle ear cavity .

Ossicles

The ossicles are 3 in number (fig.4)

Malleus

- Incus
- Stapes

Fig.4 The middle ear ossicles.(Source: Medscape)

Inf = inferior; Lat = lateral; Med = medial; Sup = superior.

Sound waves are amplified from air by ear ossicles to internal ear(perilymph).

Sound waves striking the tympanic membrane cause pressure wave in the inner ear fluid.

Eustachian tube

Middle ear and the nasopharynx are communicating through the Eustachian tube. It equalizes pressure across the tympanic membrane.

Muscles

Muscles of the middle ear include the stapedius muscle, where the neck of the stapes is connected to the posterior tympanum.

The tensor tympani tendon attaches to the handle of the malleus, tensor tympani contracts and displaces the malleus (and the tympanic membrane) medially and dampening sound vibration.

Innervation

The horizontal part of the facial nerve traverses on the medial wall in the facial canal superior to stapes footplate.

The facial nerve branch, chorda tympani supplies the tongue in its anterior 2/3rd part (carries taste sensation) and also sublingual and submandibular salivary glands. the tympanic plexus located on the promontory of the medial wall, is contributed by:

- Tympanic branch of the glossopharyngeal (Jacobson nerve) nerve
- Caroticotympanic nerves (superior and inferior): They are the sympathetic branches of carotid plexus that joins the glossopharyngeal nerve by its tympanic branch
- Communication with a branch of greater petrosal nerve

Vascular supply

The arterial supply of middle ear is by tympanic branch of the maxillary artery supplies tympanic membrane by its tympanic branch, the posterior auricular artery supplies mastoid and posterior cavity by its stylomastoid branch, middle meningeal artery (petrosal branch), ascending pharyngeal artery branch, internal carotid artery, and artery of the pterygoid canal and its branch. Superior petrosal sinus and the pterygoid plexus form the venous drainage.

Inner ear

The inner ear, conducts sound to central nervous system, and also assists in balance. Auditory transduction, the conversion of acoustic energy to electrochemical energy, takes place within the inner ear.(fig.5)

Fig.5 Inner ear in relation to middle and external ear.(Source: Medscape)

The inner ear consists of membranous labyrinth and bony labyrinth .

Fig.6 Inner ear: bony and membranous labyrinths.(Source:Medscape)

The bony labyrinth is within petrous part of temporal bone formed of bony cavities

Membranous labyrinth.

Perilymph surrounds the membranous labyrinth and within it is endolymph. The membranous labyrinth also has cochlear, vestibular, and semicircular components.(fig.6)

Vestibule

The vestibule forms central part of the bony labyrinth³³ (fig.7)

The "otolithic organs" sense linear acceleration in the horizontal and vertical planes and play an important role in sensing the direction .

Semicircular and membranous canals

Semicircular canals form bony component of labyrinth and are 3 in number placed at right angles to two other canals. These canals lie above and behind the vestibule(lateral,superior and posterior)

Fig.7 Inner ear. Ant = anterior; Inf = inferior; Lat = lateral; Sup = superior.(Source: Medscape)

They play role in balance and angular acceleration detection.

Cochlea

The inner ear harbours cochlea. The transmission of electrical energy(within endolymph) occurs to the CNS via the cochlear nerve.(fig.8)

Fig.8 Cross-section of cochlea.(Source:Medscape)

The base of the cochlea is stimulated by higher frequencies and the apex is stimulated by lower frequencies.

CHRONIC SUPPURATIVE OTITIS MEDIA

CSOM has 2 types types:

- a) Mucosal type, which is usually characterized by central perforation and affects “anterior part of middle ear cleft” and patients usually are not prone to major complications.
- b) Squamosal type and mainly affects posterosuperior part of tympanic cavity and mastoid causing life threatening complications ³⁴

In developing countries, CSOM is a significant health problem, resulting in severe local damage and life-threatening complications like lateral sinus thrombophlebitis, intracranial abscess, labyrinthitis etc. It is an important cause of preventable hearing loss in developing countries like India.

Recently, antibiotic overuse has led to critical changes in bacterial strains and their antibiotic response. This has led to complexities in combating the situation.

Thus, updated information on antibiograms and the prevalence of microorganisms in CSOM patients is required to help in the treatment modalities.

Pathways and factors affecting otitis media.

“Eustachian Tube Anatomy”

By keeping pressure equalisation, allowing the drainage of secretions from the middle ear, and impeding the entry of respiratory viruses and germs, a functioning Eustachian tube is crucial for the protection of the middle ear.

The epithelium that lines it serves as the primary barrier against organism invasion and colonisation.³⁵

The middle ear infections and inflammation that persist are caused by a combination of variables that are part of the pathogenesis of CSOM.

One of the main factors contributing to CSOM is impaired Eustachian tube function.³⁶

Microbiology

The microbiology associated with CSOM involves the presence of various micro organisms, often including fungi, in the middle ear.

Because of its ability to build biofilms and resistance to antibiotics, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is the most prevalent of these bacteria and is considered clinically important. Because it can produce toxic substances that cause tissue damage,

Staphylococcus aureus coexists with it in an inflammatory pattern.

Furthermore, a prevalent cause that may also result in cases of CSOM is *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.

The advancement of the illness can also be caused by fungal infections like *Aspergillus* and *Candida*, as well as other bacteria like *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, *Proteus* spp., and anaerobic germs like *Peptostreptococcus* spp.

and *Prevotella* spp.

Moreover, anaerobic etiological organisms are the agents of causality.

Genetics and immunology

Genetics and the immune system have a major role in the management of CSOM. For protecting against mucosal infections such as CSOM, immunoglobulins IgG, IgA, and secretory IgA are the most efficient. The mucosa of the middle ear cavity produces SIgA locally, which aids in preventing bacterial colonisation and attachment.³⁷

Complications and sequelae

Serious and sometimes fatal side effects of CSOM include conductive or sensorineural hearing loss, extracranial problems (such as facial paralysis,

Subperiosteal abscess, mastoiditis), and intracranial problems (such as meningitis, cerebral abscess).³⁸ Meningitis and brain abscesses due to CSOM can even cause death.

WHO estimates place the number of people exhibiting symptoms related to CSOM³⁸ between 65 million and 330 million, with half of those people having hearing loss.

Hearing loss (both conductive and sensorineural) is regarded as the third condition that affects older individuals' that hinders physical and mental well-being in developed countries, following arthropathy and hypertension.

On the other hand, information about these health issues is still scarce for the populations of less developed nations.

In order to lessen health problems and socioeconomic adversity by acting at the appropriate moment, it is necessary to have an accurate understanding of the incidence rate of AOM across populations.

BIOFILM

Fig.9 biofilm (source³⁹)

Pathophysiology of bacterial development of biofilms

The interactions between the microorganisms that make up the community and between the microorganisms and their surroundings result in the traits that biofilms display. Benefits to the microbial community from such attributes outweigh benefits to any single cell attributes

- 1) **Structure and adhesion.** Both biotic and abiotic surfaces can support the formation of biofilms, which can establish strong, stable attachments that makes its removal challenging and increase survival. Advanced biofilms are three-dimensional structures that have intricate communities.³⁹
- 2) **Labour division** Different genetically identical micro-organism subpopulations with distinct behaviors and metabolic activities may arise inside the biofilm as a result of the creation of distinct microenvironments. So, in order to maximize productivity and cooperation, the community may split up the tasks.³⁹

- 3) **The cycle of nutrients.** The community's microorganisms' ability to grow and survive can be facilitated by the nutrients that biofilms inside the matrix can cycle and recycle. Enzymes produced by the microorganisms in the biofilm aid in this nutrient cycle.³⁹
- 4) **Increased resilience.** Because of the biofilm matrix's protective qualities and the microorganisms' capacity for environmental adaptation, residents of biofilms are frequently more resilient to environmental disturbances than planktonic (free-living) microorganisms.³⁹
- 5) **Genetic material exchange.** Horizontal gene transfer, which permits the exchange of genetic material between several microorganisms of the same or different species, is known to occur in biofilms. This allows the biofilm community to quickly acquire new features that enable it to adapt to changing environmental conditions.³⁹
- 6) **Collective activity** Chemical signaling, also known as quorum sensing, is a common way for many microorganisms in biofilms to interact and plan their activity. As a result, the microorganisms can adapt their behavior to the biofilm environment and respond accordingly.³⁹

Fig.10 Life cycle of Biofilm (source ⁴⁰)

METHODS TO IDENTIFY BIOFILMS

The methods used for detection of biofilm.⁴¹

Method	Aim
‘Tube method (TM)’	‘Qualitative detection by observing biofilm lined on bottom and walls of tube’
‘Congo red agar (CRA)’	‘Qualitative detection by observing colony color change’
‘Microtiter plate (MtP)’	‘Quantitative detection of biofilm by microplate reader (microELISA)’
‘Real-time PCR’	‘Detection of biofilm genes’
‘Conventional PCR’	
‘Multiplex PCR’	

Biofilms are nearly impossible to detect with standard culture techniques⁴² because these methods fall short of explaining the intricate, three-dimensional nature of biofilms. Molecular diagnostics-based nucleic acid amplification

strategies have made it possible to detect and identify bacteria, and a variety of imaging technologies have helped researchers understand the role of biofilms play in human infections⁴². Another advanced resolution method that provides ultrastructure analysis of biofilms is scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

MANAGEMENT OPTIONS IN BIOFILM AFFECTED CSOM PATIENTS INVESTIGATIONS

HRCT TEMPORAL BONE

Ear pathology ranks as the third most common reason for consulting an otorhinolaryngologist, with middle ear inflammation frequently leading to antibiotic prescriptions and surgical procedures in young patients⁴³.

Previously, a diagnosis was made solely on the basis of the clinical examination in the majority of cases. Nonetheless, it was proposed that the existing strategy for preventing and treating ear infections was insufficient given the rise in the occurrence of infectious diseases. Consequently, imaging is crucial, particularly in complex and recurring illnesses, as the results might have a significant impact on the course of treatment^{44,45}.

CT is becoming more and more the imaging study of choice for conclusive preoperative temporal bone imaging since the development of helical scanning techniques.⁴⁶

When diagnosing inflammatory middle ear conditions such as cholesteatoma or chronic otitis media, as well as when evaluating the middle ear after mastoidectomy or tympanoplasty, HRCT is frequently utilized⁴⁶.

SURGICAL PROCEDURES FOR BIOFILM AFFECTED CSOM PATIENTS

TYMPANOPLASTY

With the goal of preventing reinfection and restoring hearing, tympanoplasty is the surgical process used to repair a perforated TM, with or without replacement of the ossicles (ossiculoplasty). The most frequent indication is CSOM; big invasive cholesteatomas may necessitate both TM repair and a mastoidectomy⁴⁷.

In order to reconstruct the perforated TM and restore the middle ear's sound conduction mechanism, Wullstein and Zollner developed the overlay graft technique in the 1950s, which marked the beginning of tympanoplasty history⁴⁸. Surgical techniques for tympanoplasty have evolved since then, and these developments are explained here.⁴⁸

Wullstein Classification

Wullstein classified Tympanoplasty into 5 types, ⁴⁸

- “Type I: repair of the TM alone; no middle ear abnormality. Type I tympanoplasty is synonymous with myringoplasty”
- “Type II: repair of the TM and middle ear; the malleus is eroded. Tympanoplasty involves grafting the TM to the incus”
- “Type III: repair of the TM onto the stapes head; the malleus and incus have a defect”
- “Type IV: the TM is grafted to the stapes footplate, which is movable”
- “Type V: repair involves the stapes footplate, which is fixed”

CORTICAL MASTOIDECTOMY

- “Mastoidectomy is a surgical procedure of the temporal bone that opens mastoid air cells by removing the thin bony partitions between them.”⁴⁹ types of mastoidectomy are:

Cortical : where all the mastoid air cells are exenterated

Canal wall up mastoidectomy : here the posterior bony meatal wall separating EAC from mastoid cavity is preserved

Canal wall down mastoidectomies: here posterior meatal wall is lowered and EAC and mastoid cavity are made into single cavity , mainly done for patients who have recurrent persistent COM or cholesteatoma.

The ultimate choice of surgery depends on a number of considerations, such as the patient's propensity to follow up regularly, the patient's inherent anatomy, the overall severity of the disease, and the management of any risks to hearing or balance..⁴⁹

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN: PROSPECTIVE STUDY

SOURCE OF DATA

This prospective study is conducted in the Department of Otorhinolaryngology in association with the Department of Microbiology in a tertiary care, SHRI B M PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE AND RESEARCH CENTRE AND HOSPITAL [BLDE (DU) UNIVERSITY] in Vijayapura between September 2022 TO March 2024

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA

Patients with the clinical diagnosis of CSOM attending OPD of ENT Department of our institute who satisfied the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study.

- 1) The data was collected in the form of questionnaire in terms of complete clinical history, clinical examination and necessary investigations of the patient.
- 2) Detailed examination of the patients with an emphasis on ear findings was done with the help of otoscopy to see the tympanic membrane status
- 3) Using proper aseptic precautions, a middle ear swab was collected using a sterile flocked swab
 1. Interpretation of bacterial culture
 2. Antibiotic susceptibility
 3. Biofilm production testing by
 - a. Tube method (fig.11)
 - b. Congo red agar(fig.12)

The isolates were subjected to antibiotic susceptibility testing by employing Kirby-Bauer standard disc diffusion method on Muller- Hinton agar, according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines (M100-S24).

4. A preoperative pure tone audiometry and HRCT temporal bone (coronal) and (axial) view has been done in required cases.
5. Early intervention of the patients with biofilm positive by tympanoplasty, cortical mastoidectomy, Modified radical mastoidectomy were performed.
6. Post operatively these patients were followed up at one week, 15 days, one month, three months .They were evaluated for the discharge-free period, pain-free period, graft uptake and infection-free period during follow-up.

Sample Size

With the anticipated Proportion of common organisms, Pseudomonas aeruginosa 44% the study would require a sample size of 170 to achieve a power of 80% for detecting biofilm in CSOM cases two sided p-value of 0.05 with effect size 0.11 using G* power software 3.1.9.7

Statistical analysis

All characteristics were summarized descriptively. For continuous variables, the summary statistics of mean \pm standard deviation (SD) were used.

For categorical data, the number and percentage were used in the data summaries and diagrammatic presentation. Chi-square (χ^2) test was used for association between two categorical variables.

The formula for the chi-square statistic used in the chi square test is:

$$\chi_c^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

The subscript “c” is the degree of freedom. “O” is observed value and E is expected value. $C = (\text{number of rows} - 1) \times (\text{number of columns} - 1)$

The difference of the means of analysis variables between two independent

groups was tested by unpaired t test.

The t statistic to test whether the means are different can be calculated as follows

If the p-value was < 0.05 , then the results were considered to be significant otherwise it was considered as not statistically significant. Data were analysed using SPSS software v.23 (IBM Statistics, Chicago, USA) and Microsoft office 2007.

Inclusion criteria

Patients diagnosed with Chronic suppurative otitis media.

Exclusion criteria

‘Patients suffering from CSOM who are on systemic antibiotics in the past seven days of presentation’.

‘Patients who are on topical medications to the ear’.

‘Patients having ear discharge due to some other condition like otitis externa, otomycosis etc’.

BIOFILM POSITIVE

Tube method :

Here the isolates were inoculated in polystyrene test tube containing tryptic soy broth with 1% glucose and incubated at 37 degree for 24 hours, results were interpreted by appearance of purple ring depicting biofilm positivity

Congo red agar method:

It uses a solid medium congo red agar, where directly bacterial colonies can be analysed and slime forming strains can be identified ‘black colonies on red agar’ depicting biofilm positivity was done and non slime forming strains did not change colour (red coloured colonies)

Fig.11 tube method positive for biofilms

Fig.12 Congo red agar positive for biofilms

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

A hospital-based prospective study was conducted with 170 patients to study the biofilm formation in CSOM

1. SEX DISTRIBUTION:

Out of the 170 patients studied enrolled in this study 53.5% were males and 46.5% were females. Males were more compared to females in the study .

(table.1)(fig.13)

Gender	No. of patients	Percentage
Female	79	46.5
Male	91	53.5
Total	170	100.0

Table 1. Distribution of patients according to sex

Fig.13 Gender distribution

2. AGE DISTRIBUTION

The present study included 170 patients , the most commonly affected age group was 10 to 19 years, which included 36(21.2%)patients.(table.2)(fig.14)

Age(Years)	No. of patients	Percentage
< 10	5	2.9
10 – 19	36	21.2
20 – 29	25	14.7
30 – 39	35	20.6
40 – 49	25	14.7
50 – 59	23	13.5
60 – 69	15	8.8
70+	6	3.5
Total	170	100.0

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to age (years)

Fig.14 Distribution of age

3. DISTRIBUTION ON PRESENCE OF BIOFILM

In the total sample of 170 patients 155 (91.2%) were biofilm positive and 15(8.8%) were biofilm negative.(table.3)(fig.15)

BIOFILM	No of patients	Percentage
Negative	15	8.8
Positive	155	91.2
Total	170	100.0

TABLE 3 : distribution of patients based on the presence of biofilm.

Fig.15 distribution of patients based on the presence of biofilm.

DISTRIBUTION OF ORGANISMS IN SAMPLES

Out of 155 biofilm positive patients MRSA was found in 57(33.55%) patients and coagulase negative staphylococcus isolated being lowest in 4 patients (2.4%)(table.4)(fig.16)

Fig.16 Percentage of different organisms showing biofilm positivity

Organisms	No of isolated organisms	Percentage
citrobacterfreundii	11	6.5
Coagulase negative staphylococcus	4	2.4
Escherichia coli	10	5.9
klebsiella pneumoniae	8	4.7
MRSA	57	33.5
pseudomonas aeruginosa	56	32.9
staphylococcus aureus	13	7.6
streptococcus pyogenes	4	2.4
Streptococcus pyogenes	7	4.1
Total	170	100.0

Table.4distribution of organisms based on biofilm positivity

DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS BASED ON THEIR PRE OP PAIN

In total of 170 patients 105(61.8%)patients had pre operative pain and 65(38.2%) did not have pre operative pain(table.5)(fig.17)

Pre op pain		
	No. Of patients	Percentage
No	65	38.2
Yes	105	61.8
Total	170	100.0

Table.5 Distribution of patients based on presence of preop pain

Fig.17 Distribution of patients based on presence of preoperative pain

DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS BASED ON ORGANISMS SENSITIVE TO FIRST LINE DRUGS

Out of 170 patients 135 patients(79.4%) were resistant or 35 patients(20.6%) were sensitive to drugs like ciprofloxacin, ampicillin, amoxiclav, ceftriaxone, gentamicin(table.6)(fig.18)

	No . of patients	Percentage
Resistant	135	79.4
Sensitive	35	20.6
Total	170	100.0

Table.6 Distribution of patients based on sensitivity to first line drugs

Fig.18 Distribution of patients based on sensitivity to first line drugs

DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS BASED ON ORGANISMS SENSITIVE TO HIGHER ANTIBIOTICS

Out of total 170 patients 152 were sensitive to higher antibiotics and 18 were resistant to higher antibiotics like linezolid, piperacillin tazobactam, meropenem, amikacin, tigecycline.(table.7)(fig.19)

	No of patients	Percentage
Resistant	18	10.6
Sensitive	152	89.4
Total	170	100.0

Table.7 Distribution of patients based on sensitivity to higher antibiotics

Fig.19 Distribution of patients based on sensitivity for higher antibiotics

DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS WHO UNDERWENT EARLY SURGICAL INTERVENTION

Out of total 170 patients 155 were biofilm positive and underwent early surgical intervention and 15 were biofilm negative so were not included in early surgical intervention(table.8)(fig.20)

	No. of patients	Percentage
NA	15	8.8
No	0	0
yes	155	91.2
Total	170	100.0

Table.8 distribution of patients based on early surgical intervention(NA=NOT APPLICABLE- BIOFILM NEGATIVE)

Fig.20 Distribution of patients based on early surgical intervention

COMPARISON OF PRE OP PAIN AND POST OP PAIN IN PATIENTS

In total 170 patients 99 patients had pain preoperatively ,at 1 week post operatively 47 patients had pain, at post op 15 days 30 patients had pain, at post op 1 month 9 patients had pain and at post op 3 months 8 patients had pain which showed that early surgical intervention in biofilm positive patients post op pain was reduced and was found to be statistically significant(Table.9)(fig.21)

Pain	No	Yes	Cochran's Q Test	Significant value
pre op pain	56	99	249.120	P=0.001*
post op pain 1 week	108	47		
post op pain 15 days	125	30		
post op pain 1 month	146	9		
post op pain 3 months	147	8		
*: Statistically significant				

Table.9 Comparison of pre op pain and post op pain in patients

Fig.21 Comparison of preoperative and postoperative pain

COMPARISON OF POST OP EAR DISCHARGE IN PATIENTS AT DIFFERENT INTERVALS

Out of total 155 patients with early surgical intervention , 9(5.80%) patients had discharge at post operative 1 week , 14(9.03%) patients had discharge at post op day 15, 13(8.38%) patients had discharge on post op 1 month and 3 months(table.10)(fig.22)

Discharge	No	Yes	Percentage
Post op discharge 1 week	146	9	5.80%
Post op discharge 15 days	141	14	9.03%
Post op discharge 1 month	142	13	8.38%
Post op discharge 3 months	142	13	8.38%

Table .10 Comparison of post op ear discharge in patients at different intervals

Fig.22 Comparison of post op discharge in patients at different intervals

INFECTION FREE PERIOD AND GRAFT UPTAKE POSTOPERATIVELY

In 155 patients who underwent early surgical intervention 142 (83.5%) patients had infection free period and successful graft uptake and 13 (7.6%) had graft uptake failure(Table.11)(fig.23)

Graft uptake		
	No of patients	Percentage
No	13	7.6
Yes	142	83.5
Total	170	100.0

Table.11 Number of patients having infection free period and graft uptake post operatively

Fig.23 Distribution of patients on succesful graft uptake

Infection free period * graft uptake Crosstabulation

Out of 155 patients 142(83.5%) patients had infection free period and 13(7.6%) patients persisted to have infection post operatively(table.12)

		graft uptake			
		NA	No	Yes	
infection free period	NA	15	0	0	15
		100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	8.8%
	no	0	13	0	13
		0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	7.6%
	yes	0	0	142	142
		0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	83.5%
Total		15	13	142	170
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Table.12 infection free period and graft uptake crosstabulation

NA=NOT APPLICABLE(biofilm negative)

DISCUSSION

SEX DISTRIBUTION

In our study, 170 patients were included. Out of these patients 91 (53.5%) were males while 79 (46.5%) of patients were females. In our study it was found that males were more commonly affected than females.

In a study by Priya et al, 500 patients were included. Male patients were 63% (n=315) while female patients were 37% (n = 185). Males were more affected than females⁵⁰

Luke Hunt et al conducted a study where male patients were (54.1%) and female patients were (45.9%)⁵¹

AGE DISTRIBUTION

In our study, 10-19 (21.2%) was observed to be the age group having highest CSOM incidence of all the age groups while the lowest incidence was found in patients in the age group of <10 years (2.9%).

Metri Basavaraj in India reported in a study that the CSOM patients who were most commonly affected were between the age group of 1–20 years old (52.8%), followed by 21–60 years old (45.9%)⁵².

Priya et al conducted a study which showed incidence of CSOM to be highest among patients in the age group of 20-29 years (32.8%) while the lowest was found in patients \geq 60 years age (3.2%)⁵⁰

BIOFILM POSITIVE

In our study out of total 170 patients 155 (91.2%) patients were biofilm positive and 15 (8.8%) patients were biofilm negative.

In a study done by Lee Michael Robert et al out of 10 patients Biofilms were present in six patients (60%) and negative in 4 patients (40%)⁵³

In a study conducted by Jensen, RG, Johansen et al out of 21 patients biofilm was identified in 17 patients (81%) and 4 patients(19%) were biofilm negative⁵⁴

ISOLATION OF ORGANISMS

In our study the most common organism isolated was Methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus(MRSA) 57(33.5%) cases and least common was Coagulase negative staphylococcus in 4 (2.4%) patients .

Studies conducted by Deb et al.⁵⁵ (79%) Kumar et al.⁵⁵ (46%), Poorey et al.⁵⁵ (35.2%) , and Vishwanath et al.⁵⁵ (32.2%), reported the predominant organism to be Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Staphylococcus aureus (32.75%),was the second most common organism that was comparable to the studies conducted by Deb et al. (20%)⁵⁵ and Kumar et al. (33%)⁵⁵.

Prakash et al.⁵⁶ reported in a study staphylococcus aureus (41.25%) being the predominant isolate

SENSITIVITY TO ANTIBIOTICS

In our study 135(79.4%) patients were resistant to first line antibiotics like ciprofloxacin ,ampicillin, amoxiclav, ceftriaxone, gentamicinand 152(89.4%) were sensitive for higher antibiotics like linezolid ,meropenem, tigecycline ,amikacin, piperacillin tazobactam

Vishwanath et al.⁵⁵, conducted a study that reported maximum sensitivity that organisms showed was to cotrimoxazole (95%), erythromycin (75%), moderate sensitivity to ampicillin (55%), and ciprofloxacin (45%).

Sharma et al.⁵⁷,conducted a study where maximum sensitivity that organisms showed was to piperacillin (97.3%), followed by gentamicin (73%), amikacin (78.4%), ceftazidime (91.2%), and resistance to netilmycin (2.7%).

Preoperative pain was seen in 99 (out of 105 excluding biofilm negative patients

)of the patients and 56 patients had no pain

THE ROLE OF EARLY SURGICAL INTERVENTION IN BIOFILM AFFECTED CSOM PATIENTS

In our study early surgical intervention was done in 155 biofilm positive patients 70 patients underwent cortical mastoidectomy, 55 patients underwent tympanoplasty and 30 patients underwent modified radical mastoidectomy

Postoperatively patients were followed up at 1 week , 15days , 1 month and 3 months , and it was observed that only 47, 30,9,8 patients had pain which was statistically significant($p<0.001$)

Postoperative infection free period and graft uptake was seen in 142 (83.5%) patients while 13(7.6%) patients had graft failure.

Haswani et al conducted a study which showed Surgical modalities mechanically disrupt the biofilms resulting in increased host defense mechanism⁵⁸

In a study conducted by mahdiani et al 82.5% of patients underwent surgical management, with majority patients undergoing intact canal wall procedure. Patient's were followed up after six months of surgical intervention that 426 patients (71.00%) were symptomatically better and presented with no complaints ⁵⁹

Our study shows almost same percentage of patients who had better outcomes Formation of biofilm leads to resistance and recurrence of infection in csom and explain the etiopathogenesis of CSOM. Isolation of biofilm forming patients in CSOM helps to provide proper management strategies in such CSOM cases.

Biofilm production is one of the mechanisms which leads to the bacterial resistance to antibiotics and related antimicrobial compounds (Stewart and Costerton, 2001). Biofilms eradication is difficult and also leads to recurrent infections (Donelli and Vuotto, 2014).

Hence in such cases ,early intervention is more beneficial as it helps in disrupting the bacterial residue and enhances success rate in the form of reducing pain due to infection and better healing

CONCLUSION

Occurance of biofilms is common in CSOM patients. Isolation of biofilm forming bacteria helps in better management of infection and overcome bacterial resistance. Early surgical intervention in biofilm positive csom patients would be helpful in reducing pain due to infection , and good control of infection ,hence better graft uptake

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ANNEXURE I

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

BLDE
(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)
Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956
Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)
The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA
BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 706/2022-23 30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on **Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m.** in the Department of **Pharmacology** scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "A STUDY OF BIOFILM FORMATION IN CSOM PATIENS".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: Dr. Ashwini Patil

NAME OF THE GUIDE : Dr. H. T. Lathadevi, Professor & HoD, Dept. of ENT.

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura

Dr. Akram A. Naikwadi
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutinization:

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.
BLDE (DU): Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263303, Website: www.bldedu.ac.in, E-mail: office@bldedu.ac.in
College: Phone: +918352-262770, Fax: +918352-263019, E-mail: bmpmc.principal@bldedu.ac.in

ANNEXURE – II

PROFORMA

SCHEME OF CASE TAKING

1) NAME:

CASE NO:

2) AGE:

IP NO:

3) SEX:

DOA:

4) RELIGION:

DOS:

5) OCCUPATION:

DOD:

6) RESIDENTIAL ADDRESS

7) SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS

8) CHIEF COMPLAINTS:

9) HISTORY OF PRESENTING ILLNESS:

10) PAST HISTORY:

11) GENERAL PHYSICAL EXAMINATION:

Pallor: Present/Absent

Icterus:Present/Absent

Clubbing: Present/Absent

GeneralizedLymphadenopathy: Present/Absent

Build: Poor/Medium/Well

Nourishment: Poor / Medium /Well

12) VITALS

PR:

BP:

RR:

Temp

13)OTHER SYSTEMICEXAMINATION:

- RespiratorySystem
- CardiovascularSystem
- Central NervousSystem
- Per Abdomenexamination

14) LOCALEXAMINATION

- EAR Right Left
- Pinna

- Pre auricular area
- Post auricular area
- Infra auricular area
- External auditory canal
- Discharge-type-quantity
- Tympanic membrane

Pars Tensa

Pars flaccida

- Mastoid tenderness
- Fistula sign
- Tragal tenderness
- Facial nerve function
- Nystagmus
- Tuning Fork test

1. Rinne

2. Weber

2. ABC

- NOSE

- ORALCAVITY

- OROPHARYNX

1) INVESTIGATION:

a. C/S TAKEN

1. Direct gram stain

2. Interpretation of bacterial culture

3. Swab biofilm detection

METHOD

RESULTS 1.POSITIVE

2. NEGATIVE

4. Organisms Isolated

5. Antibiotic Sensitivity

b. PURE TONE AUDIOMETRY FINDINGS

HRCT TEMPORAL BONE FINDINGS (in case needed)

Positive findings--

- 2) Final diagnosis:
- 3) Type of Surgery Done
- 4) Intraoperative finding:**
 - 1) External auditory meatus-
 - 2) Middle ear-

Mucosa/polyp/granulation tissue

Malleus

Incus

Stapes-foot plate/supra structure

Soft tissue

Sinus tympani area

Eustacian tube opening

Round window

oval window

3) Tegmen plate

4) Sinus plate

5) Sino dural angle

6) Fascial canal – tympanic part

Vertical part

Labyrinthine part

7) Semicircular canals- lateral

Posterior

Superior

8) Mastoid-fluid filled/septa

cortex

Cellularity

Antrum

Korners septum

Cholesteatoma/granulation

Follow up

-one week

discharge-free period

pain-free period

Tympanic membrane graft uptake

infection-free period

-15 days

discharge-free period

pain-free period

Tympanic membrane graft uptake

infection-free period

-one month

discharge-free period

pain-free period

Tympanic membrane graft uptake

infection-free period

-three months

discharge-free period

pain-free period

Tympanic membrane graft uptake

infection-free period

COMMENTS-

ANNEXURE –III
INFORMED CONSENT FORM
BLDE (deemed to be university)
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL AND
RESEARCH CENTRE , VIJAYAPURA- 586103.

TITLE OF THE PROJECT

“A STUDY OF BIOFILM FORMATION IN CSOM PATIENTS”

PG STUDENT - **Dr. ASHWINI PATIL**
DEPARTMENT OF OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

PG GUIDE - **Dr. H T LATHA DEVI**
DEPARTMENT OF OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY
BLDE (Deemed To Be University)
SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE
HOSPITAL AND RESEARCH CENTRE,
VIJAYAPURA – 586103

All aspects of this consent form are explained to the patient in the language understood by him/her.

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH:

I have been informed about this study. I have also been given a free choice of participation in this study.

PROCEDURE:

I am aware that in addition to routine care received, I will be asked a series of questions by the investigator. I have been asked to undergo the necessary investigations and treatment, which will help the investigator in this N study.

RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition, and the procedure of this study is not expected to exaggerate these feelings that are associated with the usual course of treatment.

BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in this study will help to improve the survival of the patient and will bring about a better outcome.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will be a part of Hospital records and will be subject to confidentiality and privacy regulation. Information of a sensitive personal nature will not be a part of the medical records but will be stored in the investigator's research file and identified only by a code number. The code-key connecting name to numbers will be kept in a separate location. If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purposes, no name will be used, and other identifiers such as photographs and audio or videotapes will be used only with my special written permission. I understand that I may see the photographs and videotapes and hear the audiotapes before giving this permission.

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time. **Dr. ASHWINI R PATIL** is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of the study, which might influence my continued participation.

If during the study or later, I wish to discuss my participation in or concerns regarding this study with a person not directly involved, I am aware that the social

worker of the hospital is available to talk with me. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

REFUSAL OR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice to my present or future care at this hospital. I also understand that DR.ASHWINI R PATIL may terminate my participation in the study after she has explained the reasons for doing so and has helped arrange for my continued care by my own physician or physical therapist if this is appropriate.

INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to me resulting directly from my participation in this study if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to me, but no further compensation would be provided. I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study, I am not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained the purpose of the research, the procedures required and the possible risks and benefits to the best of my ability in the patient's own language.

Dr. ASHWINI R PATIL

Date

(Investigator)

STUDY SUBJECT CONSENT STATEMENT

I confirm that **DR. ASHWINI R PATIL** has explained to me the purpose of the research, the study procedures that I will undergo, and the possible risks and discomforts as well as benefits that I may experience in my own language. I have read, and I understand, this consent form. Therefore, I agree to give consent to participate as a subject in this research project.

Participant / Guardian

Date

Witness to signature

Date

MASTER CHART

SL NO	NAME	AGE	SEX	Period of ear discharge	BIOFILM	organism isolated	pre op pain	antibiotic sensitivity [first line]	Antibiotic sensitivity[higher]	Early surgical intervention	post op pain 1 week	post op pain 15 days	post op pain 1 month	post op pain 3 months	post op discharge 1 week	post op discharge 15 days	post op discharge 1 month	post op discharge 3 months	infection free period	graft uptake
1	amruta	11 years	female	5 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
2	gurulingayya	70 years	male	2 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
3	vikas	18years	male	1 year	positive	klebsiella pneumoniae	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
4	mallappa	58 years	male	10 years	positive	Coagulase negative staphylococcus	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
5	kartik	9 years	male	3 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	yes	no	no	yes	yes	no	no
6	divakar	47 years	male	15 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
7	bheerappa	27 years	male	10 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
8	praveen	24 years	male	6 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
9	danappa	54 years	male	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no	no
10	jyothi	32 years	female	12 years	positive	MRSA	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
11	jyothiba	70 years	male	6 years	negative	Streptococcus pyogenes	yes	sensitive	sensitive	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
12	laxman	24 years	male	2 years	positive	Coagulase negative staphylococcus	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
13	rukamabai	42 years	female	7 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes

14	allahbaksh	48 years	male	20 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
15	hanumanth	24 years	male	6 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
16	santosh	14 years	male	2 years	negative	citrobacter freundii	no	sensitive	sensitive	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
17	nikita	27years	female	8 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
18	radhika	12 years	female	8 months	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
19	mahadev	60 years	male	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
20	mallanna	60 years	male	5 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	yes	sensitive	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
21	priyanka	8 years	female	2 years	positive	MRSA	yes	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
22	roopsingh	41 years	male	13 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
23	kaveri	18 years	female	9 months	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
24	shantabai	55 years	female	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
25	madhumita	10 years	female	3 years	positive	klebsiella pneumoniae	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
26	mallikarjun	47years	male	2 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
27	kenchappa	56 years	male	6 years	negative	streptococcus pyogenes	yes	sensitive	sensitive	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
28	nagappa	40 years	male	10 months	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
29	davalappa	13 years	male	2 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
30	renukabai	46 years	female	7 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
31	shivaraj	13 years	male	3years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
32	ambavva	58 years	female	13 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
33	santosh	10 years	male	9 months	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
34	parvati	48 years	female	11 years	positive	citrobacter freundii	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
35	siddaling	22 years	male	5 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
36	laxman	21 years	male	6 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	resistant	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
37	yankappa	20 years	male	10 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
38	kamalabai	44 years	female	20 years	negative	Streptococcus pyogenes	yes	sensitive	sensitive	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
39	jyotiba	71 years	male	30 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
40	jagadevi	34 years	female	8 years	positive	Escherichia coli	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no
41	aditya	15 years	male	15 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
42	thakaru	68 years	male	18 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes

43	basavantraya	39 years	male	6 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
44	adarsh	12 years	male	12 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
45	taskin	3 years	female	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
46	basavaraj	19 years	male	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
47	sangamesh	15 years	male	4 years	negative	Escherichia coli	no	sensitive	sensitive	na										
48	satish	8 years	male	3 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
49	ashwini	18 years	female	5 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
50	mahanadavva	35 years	female	8 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
51	savitha	19 years	female	2 years	positive	klebsiella pneumoniae	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
52	siddamma	19 years	female	15 years	positive	citrobacter freundii	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	yes	Yes
53	sugulabai	35 years	female	5 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes						
54	danamma	62 years	female	20 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	No
55	shrimant	41 years	male	10 years	negative	streptococcus pyogenes	no	sensitive	sensitive	na										
56	manjula	30 years	female	6 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes							
57	putrarappa	26 years	male	11 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes							
58	shreekanth	16 years	male	2 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes							
59	renuka	14 years	female	1 year	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes						
60	bharati	15 years	female	5 years	negative	klebsiella pneumoniae	yes	sensitive	sensitive	na										
61	rajvardhan	5 years	male	2 years	positive	Escherichia coli	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	Yes
62	vilas	15 years	male	3 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes							
63	mallamma	40 years	female	7 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes	no	No
64	savita	39 years	female	9 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	Yes
65	savitri	30 years	female	5 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	Yes
66	kushi	13 years	female	3 years	positive	citrobacter freundii	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes						
67	hanumanth	38 years	male	8 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes						
68	malingaraya	13 years	male	6 years	positive	MRSA	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes							
69	reshma	28 years	female	14 years	positive	Escherichia coli	yes	sensitive	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	yes	Yes
70	aishwarya	17 years	female	6 years	positive	Streptococcus pyogenes	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	yes	Yes
71	laxmibai	60 years	female	15 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes							

72	Renuka	36 years	female	10 years	negative	Streptococcus pyogenes	no	sensitive	sensitive	na											
73	keerti	28 years	female	28 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	No
74	shivamma	58 years	female	18 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	Yes
75	mahadevi	60 years	female	25 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes						
76	sushmita	18 years	female	2 years	positive	Escherichia coli	yes	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
77	vilas	26 years	male	7 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
78	nirmala	40 years	female	16 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes						
79	raghavendra	38 years	male	3 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	yes	Yes
80	sahana	11 years	female	1 year	positive	citrobacter freundii	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
81	kamalabai	50 years	female	20 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no	no	no	yes	Yes
82	parvathi	45 years	female	15 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
83	seeta	35 years	female	20 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	No
84	kallappa	52 years	male	12 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
85	chidanand	63 years	male	25 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	yes	Yes
86	chandram	55 years	male	15 years	negative	Escherichia coli	no	sensitive	sensitive	na											
87	hirabai	60 years	female	20 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes							
88	siddaling	22 years	male	5 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
89	parvati	32 years	female	5 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
90	basavaraj	19 years	male	7 years	positive	Streptococcus pyogenes	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
91	yogiraj	41 years	male	20 years	positive	citrobacter freundii	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
92	ravikumar	30 years	male	12 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
93	mahesh	56 years	male	17 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
94	bhagyashree	10 years	female	3 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes						
95	devendra	55 years	male	12 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	Yes								
96	bhagvantray	62 years	male	22 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes						
97	yadanagouda	11 years	male	3 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	Yes							
98	ningappa	29 years	male	6 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes								
99	tarabai	35 years	female	10 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes								
100	bhuvanesh	44 years	male	16 years	negative	citrobacter freundii	yes	sensitive	sensitive	na											

101	krutika	34 years	female	5 years	positive	klebsiella pneumoniae	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no
102	milind	60 years	male	22 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	yes						
103	supriya	36 years	female	11 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
104	gangavva	29 years	female	2 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
105	gangabhai	30 years	female	6 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
106	basavaraj	57 years	male	16 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
107	muttavva	54 years	female	26 years	positive	Escherichia coli	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	yes						
108	jayashree	60 years	female	22 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
109	jarina	54 years	female	30 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no
110	bouramma	60 years	female	20 years	negative	staphylococcus aureus	no	sensitive	sensitive	na										
111	laxmikant	27 years	male	8 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	yes	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
112	jakkamma	22 years	female	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
113	savithri	37 years	female	5 years	positive	citrobacter freundii	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
114	pooja	23 years	female	12 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	yes						
115	kallanna	44 years	male	4 years	positive	Escherichia coli	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
116	pooja	20 years	female	5 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
117	aravind	45 years	male	2 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	yes						
118	ganesh	15 years	male	1 year	positive	klebsiella pneumoniae	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
119	rakesh	29 years	male	10 years	positive	Coagulase negative staphylococcus	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	yes						
120	ganesh	30 years	male	3 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no
121	shobha	32 years	female	15 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
122	ashok	40 years	male	10 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
123	kamamma	55 years	female	6 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
124	kavita	36 years	female	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no
125	ratnamma	51 years	female	12 years	positive	MRSA	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
126	adarsh	12 years	male	6 years	negative	Streptococcus pyogenes	yes	sensitive	sensitive	na										
127	dayanand	38 years	male	2 years	positive	Coagulase negative staphylococcus	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
128	iramma	52 years	female	7 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
129	lokesh	31 years	male	20 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes

130	rajesh	40 years	male	6 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
131	pandu	43 years	male	2 years	negative	citrobacter freundii	no	sensitive	sensitive	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
132	sachin	23 years	male	8 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
133	abhishek	55 years	male	8 months	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
134	kiran	25 years	male	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
135	rajeshwari	55 years	female	5 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	yes	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
136	suhagini	36 years	female	2 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
137	amruta	34 years	female	13 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
138	bismilla	39 years	female	2 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
139	nirmala	35 years	female	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
140	madhura	38 years	female	3 years	positive	klebsiella pneumoniae	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
141	haseena	37 years	female	2 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
142	siddappa	69 years	male	6 years	negative	streptococcus pyogenes	yes	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
143	kamala	40 years	female	2 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	no	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
144	priya	39 years	female	2 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
145	yenkappa	72 years	male	7 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
146	siddappa	52 years	male	3years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
147	gangadhar	79 years	male	13 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
148	shantabai	62 years	female	9 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no
149	basanagouda	55 years	male	11 years	negative	citrobacter freundii	yes	sensitive	sensitive	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
150	sumabai	54 years	female	5 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
151	sunita	40 years	female	6 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	resistant	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
152	prasad	38 years	male	10 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
153	tarabai	53 years	female	20 years	negative	Streptococcus pyogenes	yes	sensitive	sensitive	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
154	yankappa	20 years	male	4 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
155	yamanappa	47 years	male	8 years	positive	Escherichia coli	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
156	rajeshwari	33 years	female	15 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
157	laxmibai	53 years	female	18 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
158	yallappa	76 years	male	6 years	positive	MRSA	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes

159	saybanna	21 years	male	12 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
160	shrishail	18 years	male	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
161	laxmi	29 years	female	1 year	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
162	venkatesh	48 years	male	4 years	positive	Escherichia coli	no	resistant	sensitive	no	yes	yes								
163	basavaraj	41 years	male	3 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	yes	no	no	no	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	no
164	shivappa	60 years	male	5 years	positive	staphylococcus aureus	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
165	mutturaj	15 years	male	8 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
166	sampath	18 years	male	2 years	positive	klebsiella pneumoniae	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							
167	nayana	11 years	female	7 years	positive	citrobacter freundii	no	resistant	sensitive	yes	no	no	no	no	yes	no	no	no	yes	yes
168	karan	12 years	male	5 years	positive	MRSA	yes	resistant	sensitive	yes	yes	no	yes	yes						
169	nitish	21 years	male	13 years	positive	pseudomonas aeruginosa	yes	resistant	resistant	yes	no	yes	yes							
170	ramesh	36 years	male	10 years	positive	streptococcus pyogenes	no	sensitive	sensitive	yes	no	yes	yes							

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